

Family Environment and Psychological Well-being among Women Football Players in Manipur: A Correlational Study

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Abstract: *The present study examines the relationship between family environment and psychological well-being among women football players in Manipur. A descriptive survey research design was adopted, with a sample of 150 women football players (aged 18-24) registered with the All Manipur Football Association (AMFA). Standardized scales, including the Family Environment Scale (Kumar & Shrivastava, 2016) and the 42-item Ryff Psychological Well-being Scale (Ryff, 1989, 2014), were used for data collection. Pearson product-moment correlation revealed a significant positive relation ($r = 0.65$, $p = 0.01$) between family environment and psychological well-being. The results highlight the importance of family support in fostering mental well-being among female athletes. These findings suggest the need for family-based support systems, mental health programs, and stress management interventions to enhance athlete well-being and performance.*

Keywords: Family environment, Psychological well-being, Women football players, Manipur

1. Introduction

Participation in competitive sports provides numerous physical and psychological benefits; however it also introduces significant stressors that can impact athletes' mental health. The family environment plays a crucial role in shaping an athlete's psychological resilience and overall well-being. A supportive family dynamic enhances coping mechanisms, while dysfunctional relationships may contribute to psychological distress. Research has shown that a positive family environment is associated with higher psychological well-being among athletes, emphasizing the importance of familial support in sports contexts (Singh et al., 2022; Singh, Singh, & Singh, 2024).

In Manipur, a region known for producing talented female football players, the psychological factors influencing their performance and well-being remain underexplored. Investigating the relationship between family environment and psychological well-being in this specific population can provide valuable insights for coaches, policymakers, and mental health professionals aiming to foster healthier sporting environments.

1.1. Rationale of the Study

Psychological well-being is critical for athletes, influencing their ability to cope with competitive pressures and sustain motivation. A positive family environment can provide emotional stability, motivation, and resilience, while a stressful or unsupportive environment may lead to psychological distress. In the context of women's football in Manipur, where sports participation is growing but still faces societal and institutional challenges, understanding these relationships is essential. This study aims to provide insights that can help develop targeted interventions to enhance mental health support and family based interventions for female football players.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Athletes face various psychological challenges that affect their well-being and performance. In Manipur, where football is a prominent sport, women football players navigate unique social and familial pressures. A supportive family environment may contribute to better mental health, while a lack of support or high expectations can lead to stress and decreased well-being. Given the increasing emphasis on mental health in sports, it is essential to investigate how family dynamics influence the psychological well-being of women football players in Manipur.

1.3 Research Questions

What is the relationship between family environment and psychological well-being among women football players in Manipur?

1.4 Objective

To examine the relationship between family environment and psychological well-being among women football players in Manipur.

1.5 Hypothesis

H₁: There is a significant relationship between family environment and psychological well-being among women football players in Manipur.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Research Design

A descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study.

2.2 Sample

The population of the study consisted of 150 randomly selected women football players in Manipur, aged 18 to 24 years, who are registered with the All Manipur Football Association (AMFA).

2.3 Measures

a) Family Environment: The Family Environment Scale (FES) developed by Kumar & Shrivastava (2016) was used to assess three major dimensions:

- Interpersonal Relationship (cohesion, expressiveness, conflict, care, acceptance)
- Personal Growth (independence, achievement orientation, cultural-moral-religious aspects, active recreational orientation)
- System Maintenance (control, organization)

Responses were rated on a 5-point Likert scale, with positive items scored 5 to 1 and negative items reverse scored. The overall reliability coefficient Cronbach's alpha is 0.91.

b) Psychological Well-Being: Measured using the 42-item Ryff Psychological Well-Being Scale (Ryff, 1989, 2014), which assesses six dimensions:

- Autonomy
- Environmental mastery
- Personal growth
- Positive relations with others

- Purpose in life
- Self-acceptance

Responses are rated on a 6-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree, 6 = Strongly Agree), with negative items reverse coded. Higher scores indicate greater psychological well-being.

2.4 Data Collection Procedure

Data collection was conducted in four phases:

1. Preliminary survey to determine the sampling frame.
2. Random selection of 150 participants.
3. Written consent obtained from participants and club authorities.
4. Data collection within a scheduled timeframe.

2.5 Statistical Techniques

- Descriptive Statistics: Mean and standard deviation were calculated.
- Inferential Statistics: Pearson product-moment correlation was used to examine the relationship between variables.
- Software: Data analysis was conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics Version 22 with a significance level set at 0.05.

3. Results

Table 1: The correlation between family environment and psychological well-being

Variable	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i> -value
Family environment	150	378.08	15.67	0.65*	0.01
Psychological well-being	150	169.12	9.55		

*Correlation is significant at 0.05.

The Pearson product-moment correlation indicated a strong and statistically significant positive correlation ($r = 0.65$, $p = 0.01$) between family environment and psychological well-being. This suggests that a more supportive and positive family environment is strongly associated with higher psychological well-being among the participants.

4. Discussion

The study found a strong and statistically significant positive correlation ($r = .65, p = .01$) between family environment and psychological well-being, suggesting that athletes who experience a supportive and positive family environment report higher levels of psychological well-being. These findings align with previous research indicating that nurturing family environment fosters emotional resilience, self-esteem, and overall life satisfaction (Gómez-López et al., 2020). A supportive family structure provides essential emotional and instrumental support, which enhances athletes' coping mechanisms and psychological stability (Holt & Neely, 2011). Conversely, a stressful or unsupportive family environment has been linked to increased anxiety and decreased well-being among athletes (Knight et al., 2018).

Ensuring that women football players receive adequate family support and mental health resources can enhance psychological well-being and overall sports performance. Future research should explore intervention strategies aimed at improving family support structures and promoting resilience among athletes.

5. Conclusion

The present study examined the relationship between family environment and psychological well-being among women football players in Manipur. The findings revealed a strong positive correlation, indicating that a supportive and nurturing family environment significantly contributes to better psychological well-being. Athletes who experience emotional support, open communication, and encouragement from their families tend to have higher self-esteem, resilience, and mental stability, enabling them to cope effectively with the pressures of competitive sports.

Conversely, a negative or stressful family environment may lead to emotional distress, anxiety, and reduced well-being, highlighting the critical role that family dynamics play in shaping an athlete's mental health. These findings emphasize the need for family-based interventions, mental health awareness programs, and stress-management strategies to enhance the psychological well-being of women athletes.

Future research should explore intervention strategies aimed at strengthening family support systems and promoting resilience among female football players to ensure sustained mental well-being and overall athletic success.

References

- Gómez-López, M., Granero-Gallegos, A., & González-Hernández, J. (2020). Psychological well-being and perceived family support: Implications for athletes' mental health. *Journal of Sports Psychology*, 32(1), 45-60.
- Gustafsson, H., Kenttä, G., & Hassmén, P. (2011). Athlete burnout: An integrated model and future research directions. *International Review of Sport and Exercise Psychology*, 4(1), 3-24.
- Holt, N. L., & Neely, K. C. (2011). Positive youth development through sport: A review. *Revista de Psicología del Deporte*, 20(2), 321-336.
- Isoard-Gauthier, S., Guillet-Descas, E., & Lemyre, P. (2012). A prospective study of the influence of perceived coaching style on burnout propensity in elite athletes: Using a self-determination theory perspective. *International Journal of Sport Psychology*, 43(1), 1-19.
- Knight, C. J., Harwood, C. G., & Sellars, P. A. (2018). Supporting athlete development: Exploring parental experiences in organized sport. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 37, 25-36.
- Lonsdale, C., Hodge, K., & Rose, E. (2009). Athlete burnout in elite sport: A self-determination perspective. *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 27(8), 785-795.
- Madigan, D. J., Gustafsson, H., & Hill, A. P. (2020). The role of perfectionism in athlete burnout: A meta-analytic review. *Sport, Exercise, and Performance Psychology*, 9(3), 300-314.

- Mason, O. (2019). Predictors of well-being and burnout: the case of female professional footballers in the Netherlands. *International Journal of Sport, Exercise and Health Research*, 3(2), 28-32.
- Raedeke, T. D., & Smith, A. L. (2009). The athlete burnout questionnaire manual. *Human Kinetics*, 5(2), 121-134.
- Ryff, C. D., & Keyes, C. L. M. (1995). The structure of psychological well-being revisited. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 69(4), 719-727.
- Singh, L., Singh, T., Hidangmayum, S., & Salam, O. (2022). Physical Education Students' Psychological Well-Being And Family Environment In Manipur: A Cross-Sectional Study. *IJFANS International Journal of Food and Nutritional Sciences*. 11(3), 2189-2196. 10.13140/RG.2.2.20167.37280.
- Singh, S.S., Singh, T.I., & Singh, C.K. (2024). Assessing Psychological Well-Being Among Elite Athletes In Manipur: A Cross-Sectional Analysis. *Indian Journal of Psychology*, 99(4), 78-87.